

THE MOST EFFECTIVE METHODS TO LEARN FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT THE SAME TIME

ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ

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Annotatsiya

To be competent in their field or know the latest technologies, a person needs to know foreign languages. Therefore, today the demand for polyglot specialists is very huge. The article discusses some problems associated with learning two foreign languages.

Компетентность в своей сфере, а также новейшие технологии требуют знаний иностранных языков. Поэтому сегодня спрос на специалистов полиглотов очень огромен. В исследовании рассматриваются некоторые проблемы, связанные с изучением двух иностранных языков.

Kalit so'z

parallel learning, French, number, bilingualism, lexical similarity, adjective agreement, busy schedule, language learning.

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Today, learning foreign languages is a modern requirement as well as one of the most necessary processes in the development of a society, but not just an interest. Also, knowing other languages teaches how to communicate with people, who are from various parts of the world, and how to make contacts with them. In particular, many scientists commented on language, including the German scientist and thinker *Goethe* expressed his views: "The more languages a person knows, the more time he/she is a human being". Therefore, people would prefer to learn two languages at the same time to gain an acquisition of multiple languages in a reasonable period of time. Although it provokes quite challenging situations like the existence of confusion in your brain during the *parallel-learning*, there are sufficiently impressive and effective ways for such circumstances. These are depicted one by one below.

1. Pair familiar languages according to the grammatical characters.

Inevitably, languages involve the differences but each has its own logic, while some grammatical rules are completely different from each other, some are almost the same [1]. For this reason, one of the best ways to study grammar topic is to compare it with another second language topic. Especially, we consider this method in the example of *French and Russian*. Learning these two languages simultaneously is really effective because it represents almost the same in terms of grammar. For instance, both are based on gender *and number*, as well as in these languages there is a tendency to attribute depending on the genus and number while the possessive pronouns are also compatible with words which come together in a sentence. We can see these rules in the tables 1,2 and 3.

Table 1.

The agreement of French adjectives in gender and number [3].

adjective	Singular		Plural	
	masc	fem	masc	fem
beautiful	beau	belle	beaux	bells
New	nouveau	nouvelle	nouveaux	nouvelles

Table 2.

The agreement of Russian adjectives in gender and number [2]

adjective	Singular		Plural
	м.р	ж.р	
red	красный шарф	красная лента	красные ленты
beautiful	красивый шарф	красивая лента	красивые ленты

Table 3.

Possessive pronouns in French and Russian

gender	French	Russian
fem	ma	МОЯ
masc	mon	МОЙ
plural	mes	МОИ

Learning these two languages at once by comparing these grammatical similarities ensures that learners will be able to master them at ease in a short period of time.

2. By focusing on lexical similarities

There are many similar words, in Latin and Greek sometimes all of them sounding the same. For example, it is reflected

in the suffixes in Russian the suffix *ция* is almost similarly said in Spanish, Italian, French and English (“sion”, “zione”, “tion”). This situation can also be clearly seen in the example of words.

Table 4.

Lexical similarities between French and English

French	English
mêmoire	memory
idée	idea
exemple	example
préférer	prefer
détester	detest
finir	finish
aider	aid
présenter	present
exuser	excuse

3. By making a *generous schedule* for everyday learning

It is utterly obvious that people confront complicated situations which learning two languages simultaneously results in if they do not make a realistic plan for each subject [4]. Learners cannot control time management, accomplish expected outcomes as well.

It is the best to set aside 3 days for each foreign language during the week. For example, if you are learning English and French or Korean (it is optional) at once, this method is one of the most suitable methods: English on Mondays and Thursdays, French or Korean on Wednesdays and Saturdays. This will definitely ensure that you have enough time to learn new information and complete tasks efficiently in a timely manner. There will also be enough distance so that the languages do not interfere with each other. This method was proven by scientists, for instance, in June 2020 the researchers Ting Khuang, Rasmus Steinkrauss and Marjolijn Verspoor conducted a study on how effective it is to learn two languages simultaneously [5]. In the research the scientists observed those who were learning one language and those who were learning two languages at the same time. The students were all studying English for 16 hours a week with the double major students also allotting extra 8 hours to the second language. What the results showed is that there was very little notable difference between the English writing abilities of the two groups of students as they progressed over time. By some measures the students who were learning two languages actually scored higher on average. So, basically, when students learn two languages based on a realistic plan, they can learn better than those who learn one language.

4. *Learn one thing* in two languages

What does it mean to learn one thing in *two languages*? It implies two processes. The first one is that you have learned a noun in English grammar. What is it? What is its function in a sentence? And so on. After this, you have to organize the same things

like that in the language which is your second parallel learning language. Furthermore, the second refers to utilize this method in a lexical way to enrich vocabulary in either French and Russian. For instance, as soon as you pass a new topic about the homeland in French, get used to gathering information about it in Russian. It leads to a significant increase in your vocabulary in both languages at the same time. Therefore, this method is a useful and effective way of learning a language.

Conclusion. All things considered, in learning any language, the first thing to do is to be patient and understand that the process takes a long time. Obviously, sometimes humanity can easily accomplish something but some things like learning two languages at once require them to handle a lot. If those who study two languages at once learn by the approaches mentioned above, they can achieve their expected goals at least a little easier.

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